

Electrochemistry of Fluoride Solutions. Part VI. Electrodeposition of Nickel from Fluoride Solutions

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The electrodeposition of nickel from acid fluoride solutions has been studied. The decomposition, discharge, and anodic dissolution potentials of Ni in acid baths have been determined. Nickel dissolves continuously at the anode without any signs of passivity. The nature of the deposits from different solution and the effect of addition agents on deposits have been studied. Hydrogen peroxide proved to be the best addition agent in acid fluoride solutions. The operating conditions for the acid fluoride bath with hydrogen peroxide as the addition agent have been specified. This bath, which yields much better deposits than any other acid bath, deserves a high place in the list of nickel plating baths.

Marino (B.P. 2316/1912) patented the use of fluoride and fluoride-tartrate solutions for depositing nickel on aluminium by immersion, aided by an electric current. Smith (*Trans. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1915, 27, 28) reported the electrolytic separation of cobalt from nickel in ammoniacal fluoride solution. Strong ammoniacal fluoride solutions were also employed by Edmister and Cooper (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 2419) for estimating nickel electrolytically. Brown (U. S. P. 2,550,449/1951) took out a patent to cover the use of fluoride solutions containing boric acid and organic brighteners for depositing nickel. These are the only references to be found in literature on the electrolytic use of nickel fluoride solutions. The electrochemistry of nickel fluoride thus appears to have been neglected and no coherent and systematic data are available to enable us to form a definite view about the suitability of nickel fluoride for nickel plating. The present investigation was undertaken to obtain the required information.

The normal fluoride of nickel is only slightly soluble in water, but the solubility is reasonably good in solutions of hydrofluoric acid. The present investigation has therefore been carried out with acid fluoride baths and data obtained on (a) decomposition and discharge potentials of acid nickel fluoride as well as the dissolution potential of nickel in the same solution, (b) nature of cathodic deposits from neutral and acid fluoride baths with and without the addition of inorganic and organic agents, and (c) porosity of different deposits obtained under different conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nickel Fluoride Solutions

Acid Solutions.—The precautions and experimental technique in dealing with fluoride and acid fluoride solutions have been detailed in the earlier publications in this series.

Nickel carbonate (C. P.) was added to hydrofluoric acid until a precipitate just began to appear (Mellor, "Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", 1936, Vol. 15, p. 402; Edmister and Cooper, *loc. cit.*). The precipitate was filtered and the filtrate used for experiments.

Neutral Solutions.—The addition of nickel carbonate to hydrofluoric acid was continued even after the appearance of a precipitate until effervescence had completely ceased. The insoluble matter at this stage was filtered and the neutral filtrate was used whenever required.

Analysis.—The estimation of nickel was made by the cyanide method. Preliminary experiments with mixtures of known amount of nickel sulphate and hydrofluoric acid containing HF/NiSO₄ ratios up to 37 showed that the method was capable of providing accurate results with acid fluoride solutions. The details and precautions enumerated by Mellor and Thomson ("A Treatise on Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 1938) were strictly adhered to and the cyanide solution was standardised against recrystallised Merck's C.P. grade nickel ammonium sulphate.

The amount of hydrofluoric acid remaining unneutralised in the acid solutions was calculated by difference. The quantity of free hydrofluoric acid was always so great in proportion to NiF₂ that the measurement of pH was not made as being of no particular significance.

Porosity Tests.—The porosity of nickel plates on copper specimens was tested by the ferroxyl test using potassium ferrocyanide instead of the usual ferricyanide. The porous spots are indicated by red coloured spots.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Potential Measurements

The potential measurements are summarised in Table I. The discharge potential measurements were made with reference to a saturated calomel electrode and the values reduced to the hydrogen scale.

TABLE I

Solution composition.	Decomposition potential.		Discharge potentials.			Disolution potential of nickel.	
	1st break.	2nd break	Anode.	Cathode		1st break.	2nd break.
				1st break.	2nd break.		
1. 0.3214M-NiF ₂ } 0.6806M-HF	1.68	2.17	1.73	0.05	-0.35		
2. 0.2280M-NiF ₂ } 0.4960M-HF	1.67	2.18	1.71	0.04	-0.36		
3. 0.1205M-NiF ₂ } 0.2575M-HF	1.71	2.17	1.74	0.03	-0.40	0.07	2.65
4. 0.2280M-NiF ₂ } 0.4960M-HF 0.2820g./litre H ₂ O ₂ }	0.84	1.27	0.86	0.02	-0.26		

The first decomposition potential and the first break in the cathode current-potential curve are, as observed earlier by Talaty (*this Journal*, 1952, 29, 149), due to the discharge of the trace impurity copper in the hydrofluoric acid. This disappears after the first few minutes of electrolysis.

The discharge potentials of nickel (in the range of -0.35 to -0.40 volt depending on the concentration of nickel) are much more negative than what should be expected from a consideration of the normal electrode potential of the metal (-0.23 volt on the hydrogen scale) and the concentrations of nickel salt in the solutions. Much greater discrepancies have been known in the deposition of nickel, iron, and cobalt from solutions of their sulphates at room temperatures. Further, it is also known that chlorides and other halides reduce the magnitude of this discrepancy and cause the metals to be deposited at values much closer to the reversible values. No satisfactory explanation of this phenomenon has been advanced, but it is clear that irreversibility of some sort and interference with the usual processes of ion discharge and metal deposition are present in these cases. What is more interesting and relevant to the present case, however, is the greater proximity of the cathode discharge potentials to the reversible values in fluoride solutions than in sulphate baths and this itself is a point in favour of the fluoride baths. The dissolution potential of nickel in a solution (0.1205*M*-NiF₂ and 0.2575*M*-HF) was measured. Two breaks, the 1st at 0.07 and the 2nd at 2.65, were observed in the current anode potential curve (Fig. 1). That the first is the dissolution potential of Ni whereas the second corresponds to oxygen discharge was established by actual experiment. What is noteworthy here, however, is the fact that the nickel anode continued to dissolve even at higher potentials in spite of the evolution of oxygen, without any exhibition of passivity—a phenomenon quite so different from what is found in sulphate solutions.

FIG. 1 0.2280*M*-NiF₂, 0.4960*M*-HF. 29°.

Electrodeposition of the Metal

The experiments were all carried out at room temperature (29-30°) with agitation of the electrolyte. The anode consisted of a plate of pure nickel. Initially deposits were obtained on platinum cathodes and later on copper cathodes. For all tests the deposition was continued usually for one hour.

Neutral fluoride solutions proved unsatisfactory, the deposits obtained being dark and non-adherent. The addition of neutral sodium and potassium fluorides did not improve deposits very much. Acid fluoride solutions proved more effective. The deposits were compact and solid, fine grained but rather dull in colour in concentrated solutions. Acid fluoride solutions at comparatively low dilutions gave much better deposits. The deposits were sufficiently lustrous and adherent, but at reasonable current densities there was a tendency for the deposits to grow 'trees' or 'whiakers' at the edges of the plates.

The most favourable concentrations for the acid fluoride bath were found to be 0.2280*M*-NiF₂ and 0.4960*M*-HF. Except, where otherwise stated, trials were always conducted with a cathodic current density of 4.0 amp./dm².

The addition of small quantities of ammonium fluoride to the acid bath improved the cathode current efficiency as well as the nature of the deposit; when the addition was above 0.5 g./litre, the deposit deteriorated. The maximum current efficiency observed at the cathode was 80% when the cathode current density employed was 4 amp./dm². The anode current efficiency was invariably higher than 100% in acid baths, indicating that free hydrofluoric acid present in the baths had considerable corrosive effect on a nickel surface, freshly formed by anodic dissolution.

Influence of Addition Agents

The following addition agents were investigated: (1) peptone, (2) thiourea, (3) naphthalene- β -sulphonic acid, (4) glucose, (5) gelatine, (6) gelatine + naphthalene- β -sulphonic acid, (7) brucine, (8) hydrogen peroxide. Almost all of these improved the appearance of the deposit to some extent, glucose, gelatine, and hydrogen peroxide being the most effective even when small quantities were added.

Hydrogen peroxide proved to be the best agent for obtaining smooth deposits while maintaining good cathode efficiency. The deposits were good, entirely free from pits, quite lustrous, and nonporous. The optimum concentration by hydrogen peroxide was determined to be 0.2820 g./litre in the bath. Further increase in the concentration of this addition agent rendered the deposit duller and somewhat brittle. The nature of the deposit and other conditions are detailed in Table II.

TABLE II

Influence of the addition of hydrogen peroxide.

Solution = 0.2280*M*-NiF₂ - 0.4960*N*-HF. Current density = 4.0 amp./dm².

Cathode: Copper, except when mentioned otherwise.

No.	Hydrogen peroxide (g./litre).	Applied voltage.	Cathode efficiency.	Nature of deposit.
1.	0.0202	2.65	65.23	Deposit much smoother and brighter than without addition agent.
2.	0.0404	2.55	68.52	Deposit much better than in (1).
3.	0.1010	2.55	67.42	Same as in (2).
4.	0.1614	2.50	67.82	Better than in (3).
5.	0.2017	2.40	69.16	Ductile, lustrous and fine.
6.	0.2820	2.30	70.53	Lustrous, ductile, fine-grained, and smooth. The deposit took on a very high polish on buffing more easily than in any previous case.
7.	0.3600	2.25	69.82	About the same as in (6).
8.	0.6802	2.35	63.02	Deposit became somewhat brittle and edges of the plate were thicker and rougher.

Data in Table II indicate the excellence of the acid fluoride bath when hydrogen peroxide is used with the addition agent (the optimum concentration being 0.2820 g./litre).

The figures recorded in the last horizontal row of Table I point to the further advantage of this bath in that the addition of hydrogen peroxide lowers the decomposition potential very considerably, thus reducing the voltage to be applied for maintaining any given current density. Figs. 2 and 3 (A and B) indicate two causes for the lowering of the decomposition potential. Firstly, hydrogen peroxide exerts a depolarising effect at the cathode and the cathode discharge potential is brought much nearer to the reversible potential (differing from

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FIG. 2. 0.2280M NiF₂, 0.4960MHF; H₂O₂, 0.2820 g/L 29°.

FIG. 3A. 0.1205M NiF₂, 0.2575M HF. 29°.

FIG. 3B. 0.1295M NiF₂, 0.2575M HF. 29°.

the latter only by 0.02 volt). Such proximity is rather unusual for a metal like nickel and thus constitutes a great advantage of this bath over all other baths for nickel plating. Secondly, the presence of hydrogen peroxide has lowered anode polarisation and potential. The value for anode discharge potential found here (0.86 volt) is very nearly the same as the one found by Hickling and Wilson (*J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1951, **98**, 425) for anodic discharge potential for hydrogen peroxide solutions (0.84-8.70 volt) in sulphuric acid over a wide range of concentrations.

It was felt important to determine the rate of disappearance of hydrogen peroxide from the bath, in the light of the inference in the previous paragraph. It was found very surprising that less than 1/3 of the total peroxide had disappeared in the course of continuous electrolysis for twelve hours and it was found that replenishment to the required extent once in twelve hours was quite adequate to run the bath continuously.

Cathode current efficiency has been indicated in Table II and it is quite as good as may be expected in an acid bath.

Porosity of Deposits

Typical deposits on copper electrodes from different baths were subjected to porosity tests. In all cases, the deposits were obtained by electrolysis for a period of one hour at a current density of 4 amp./dm².

TABLE III
Acid fluoride baths.

No.	Substance added.	Remarks.
1.	No addition agent	Non-porous
2.	Am. fluoride	"
3.	Sod. fluoride	"
4.	Sod. carbonate	"
5.	Pot. carbonate	"
6.	Peptone	Very porous
7.	Brucine	"
8.	Gelatine	"
9.	Napthalene sulphonic acid	Non-porous
10.	Glucose	"
11.	Hydrogen peroxide	"

It would thus be seen that in most cases the deposit is non-porous. The operating conditions of the bath giving the best results are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Solution composition	..	0.2280M-NiF ₂ , 0.4960M-HF; H ₂ O ₂ , 0.2820 g./litre.)
Cathode current density	..	4.0 amp./dm ² , with agitation of the electrolyte.
Anode current density	..	2.0 amp./dm ²
Applied potential	..	2.3 volts
Temperature	..	29°
Cathode current efficiency	..	70.53%
Anode current efficiency	..	104.53%

From this study, it is concluded that the best fluoride bath, described above, deserves recognition for a high place in the list of good, low-pH nickel-plating baths.